

Data Analytics for Technology Acceptance Monitoring of SBC Technologies

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Extended Abstract

The increasing demand for traveler clearance at Border Crossing Points (BCPs) has motivated research for finding more efficient solutions. Thus, Automated Border Control (ABC) is emerging as a solution to enhance the convenience of travelers, the throughput of BCPs, and national security. Despite the growing interest in novel Smart Border Control (SBC) technologies, there is currently a lack of information regarding their acceptance, both from travelers' and border control staff's viewpoint. The goal of our research is to provide a descriptive analytics framework for technology acceptance monitoring of SBCs aiming to enhance policy development and decision support.

Our proposed framework encompasses the lifecycle of data from the moment they are collected until their presentation to the stakeholders. Initially, the following categories of data assets have been identified as relevant: (1) indicators of acceptance, including social media data, smiley-faced terminals etc.; (2) demographics and user characteristics, such as age, travel habits, cultural background etc.; (3) objective measurements from SBC technologies, such as access time, time to capture biometrics, or situational factors, such as flight delay; and (4) factors which influence acceptance, such as perceived ease of use, perceived impact on health, etc. These data are captured either in real-time, for instance Twitter data, or using traditional methods, such as questionnaires. The collected data are harmonized using a data model developed specifically for this purpose, and then, are fed to a data analytics pipeline for pre-processing and analysis. Finally, the output of this analysis and the uncovered patterns are visually displayed to the stakeholders (i.e. policy officials and border control officers), through an interactive dashboard.

We developed a novel data model in order to standardize the data needed to assess the acceptance of SBC technologies. The model was developed by applying a hybrid approach, leveraging both related studies using NLP approaches (data-driven), and knowledge of domain experts (knowledge-based). For the data-driven approach, research papers and text documents from domain literature were pre-processed, as part of an NLP pipeline, and the most significant terms were obtained using Topic Modelling and Keyword Extraction. The implementation was done using Python libraries (YAKE, KeyBERT, Gensim, etc). For the knowledge-based approach, expert knowledge was used to derive relationships and complete the identified entities and attributes. The synthesis of the complementary approaches resulted in the data model, which was provided for feedback to experts, based on completeness, simplicity, accuracy, conciseness and adaptability. The data model is openly available.

Once data harmonization is attained using the above-mentioned model, data are fed to the framework's core, the Data Analytics Engine, whose purpose is to derive meaningful conclusions, by pre-processing, transforming, fusing and applying Data Analytics and ML techniques to the data. The approach is threefold: (1) analysis of unstructured data (text); (2) processing and analysis of structured data and; (3) cross-tabular analytics and correlations analysis between data of various formats from heterogeneous sources.

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Regarding textual data, from social media, reviews, etc. a pipeline using Natural Language Processing (NLP) approaches has been developed. It has multi-lingual capabilities and can handle text in various languages, either using text translation, or pre-trained deep learning autoencoders, such as BERT. Once the language is detected, text is pre-processed and then analyzed, where the outputs of the pipeline among others include Sentiment Analysis (Sentiment classification, Subjectivity classification), Topic Modelling (by employing LDA, LSA, HDP and other algorithms), Context of discussion, Keyword Extraction, Named Entity Extraction, and finally Descriptive Analytics, such as trends over time, geolocation analytics, etc. The pipeline was developed using Python and NLP packages, including Gensim, SpaCy, VADER, TextBlob, BERT. For Twitter specifically, 200,000 tweets were retrieved from Twitter API v2 using keywords such as “automated border control”, “smart borders”, “ETIAS”, “EES”, “e-gates”, “fingerprint”, “iris scanner”, translated also to other languages to obtain a multi-lingual dataset, and were then anonymized and translated into the FIWARE Smart Data Model before being forwarded to the NLP pipeline.

For structured data, a dedicated pipeline is implemented for pre-processing, transforming, and analyzing data from various sources, namely BCPs, deployed SBC technologies, questionnaire data, flight, cruise, and road information data etc. The data are first prepared (filtering, pre-processing and cleaning, outliers’ removal, feature extraction and engineering, feature scaling and selection) and after the application of any selected algorithm, the ML model is evaluated and fine-tuned before being deployed. Moreover, the data are analyzed using aggregation, cross-tabular statistics, correlations analysis, trends and more. Finally, data from various locations and formats and the outputs of the described pipelines are combined and analyzed, by fusing external data and aggregating data across BCPs to provide insights.

In order to visualize the results, an interactive dashboard is being developed, using Superset, a lightweight, and open-source BI application. The aim is to enable stakeholders to interactively monitor the acceptance, observe trends and changes in the acceptance and its influencing factors, explore the analytics pipelines’ output, filter, zoom in specific time periods, view raw data, and potentially perform basic self-service analytics.

Currently, a prototype has been developed and initial experiments with social media data (Twitter), and data collected from a specific BCP, have been conducted. Moreover, biases referring to various stages, from data collection, pre-processing and analysis have been considered and continuous effort is being put into their mitigation, by including the notions of fairness and balanced representation of the data assets. When the data collection is finalized and the functionalities of the system are fully implemented, the solution is going to be evaluated by domain experts. We expect that the insights and findings will enable evidence-based policy and decision support regarding the acceptance monitoring of SBC technologies.

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